

Synthetic modification of β -sitosterol with 2-amino-1,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-hydroxy-2-deoxy- β -D-glucopyranose hydrochloride

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Abstract : Coupling of β -sitosterol with glucosamine yields glucoside which has enhanced bioavailability due to number of polar groups present in the glucoside and is expected to possess enhanced anti-arthritis activity due to synergistic effects of both anti-arthritis drugs.

Keywords : β -Sitosterol, glucosamine, anti-arthritis.

Introduction

β -Sitosterol is one of the several phytosterols with chemical structure based on stigmasterol skeleton. While β -sitosterol has a chemical structure that is very similar to cholesterol yet it is only manufactured by plants, not by mammals. β -Sitosterol possess various pharmacological activities including anti-oxidant, anti-cancer¹, anti-diabetic², anti-arthritis³, anti-microbial⁴, anti-hyperlipidemic⁵, anti-inflammatory⁶, etc. We have tried to increase its anti-arthritis activity by combining it with glucosamine⁷ which is also known for its anti-arthritis activity⁸. Moreover, as glucosamine is a sugar⁹, it will therefore, increase its water solubility and hence its bioavailability.

Results and discussion

The required starting material 3,4,6-tri-*O*-acetyl-2-deoxy-2-phthalimido- β -D-glucopyranosyl bromide (3) was synthesized by treating glucosamine hydrochloride (1) with triethylamine, phthalic anhydride, sodium methoxide, NaOH, acetic anhydride and pyridine. This will form 1,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-acetyl-2-deoxy-2-phthalimido- β -D-glucopyranose (2). The acetyl group at anomeric position was converted into bromo group using HBr-AcOH so that it could react with β -sitosterol. Compound 3 thus formed was then treated with β -sitosterol in the presence of silver carbonate and silver perchlorate. Molecular sieves (4 Å) were added to the reaction mixture for reaction to

take place under dry conditions. This will result in formation of phthalimido glycoside (4). Deprotection of phthalimido group was then done using hydrazine hydrate in acetic anhydride and pyridine which results in formation of compound 5. Finally, the sugar was deacetylated using sodium methoxide in methanol. The various reactions are shown in Scheme 1.

The final compound shows increased bioavailability due to the presence of number of polar groups. It also shows enhanced anti-arthritis activity due to synergistic effect of both β -sitosterol and glucosamine.

Experimental^{10,11}

Reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial suppliers. The purity of synthesized compounds was ascertained by thin layer chromatography on silica gel G in various solvent systems using ceric ammonium sulphate as detecting agent. ¹H NMR was recorded on Brüker (dpx 200) spectrometer, chemical shifts were recorded in parts per million with TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were obtained on mass spectrometer (Brüker). Column chromatography was run on silica gel (200 ~ 300 mesh).

1,3,4,6-Tetra-O-acetyl-2-deoxy-2-phthalimido- β -D-glucopyranose (2) : Compound 2 was synthesized using glucosamine hydrochloride (1) (21.6 g, 100 mmol) in so-

Note

Reagents : (a) Et₃N, phthalic anhydride, sodium methoxide, NaOH, 50 °C, then Ac₂O, pyridine, room temperature (b) HBr-AcOH, room temperature. (c) Ag₂CO₃, silver perchlorate, molecular sieves (4 Å), β-sitosterol (d) NH₂NH₂ H₂O, heating, then Ac₂O, pyridine. (e) NaOMe-MeOH

Scheme 1

dium methoxide solution (prepared from 2.3 g/0.1 atm of sodium in 100 ml of methanol). After shaking for 10 min, the separated sodium chloride was removed by filtration and washed with methanol (50 ml). The combined filtrates were treated with finely ground phthalic anhydride (7.4 g, 50 mmol) and shaken for 10 min. Triethylamine (10.1 g, 100 mmol) was then added and the clear solution was treated with phthalic anhydride (8.1 g, 55 mmol). After shaking for 10 min, a crystalline solid started to precipitate. The mixture was then brought to 50 °C and stirred for 20 min. After being kept at 0 °C for 1 h, the solid (20.5 g) was collected by filtration and dried. Drying overnight in air resulted in the loss of triethylamine. Evaporation of the filtrate gave a yellow solid which was suspended in diethyl ether (200 ml) and collected by filtration. The products were combined (46.5 g, 82%) and treated with pyridine (200 ml) and acetic anhydride (100 ml), at room temperature for 16 h. The solu-

tion was poured into ice-water and the aqueous mixture was subsequently extracted with chloroform for three times each with 100 ml. The combined extracts were washed successively with cold water, 3% HCl, saturated NaHCO₃ solution and water. Solvent removal left yellow foam that was dissolved in diethyl ether (500 ml) and treated with charcoal. Concentration to a volume of 150 ml and storage overnight at 0 °C gave a colorless solid. The pure β-anomer can be obtained by crystallization from ethanol and recrystallization from ethyl acetate. ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ (ppm) : 1.9 (3H, s, -OCOCH₃), 2.04 (3H, s, -OCOCH₃), 2.11 (3H, s, -OCOCH₃), 2.17 (3H, s, -OCOCH₃), 3.9–4.2 (4H, m, -CH-OCOCH₃), 4.76 (1H, dd, -CH), 4.9 (1H, m, -CH), 6.5 (1H, d, -CH, *J* 8.20 Hz), 7.70 (2H, m, aromatic), 8.2 (2H, m, aromatic).

3,4,6-Tri-O-acetyl-2-deoxy-2-phthalimido-β-D-glucopyranosyl bromide (3) : A solution of compound 2 (9.54 g, 20 mmol) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) in a

saturated hydrogen bromide solution of glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was kept at room temperature for 24 h. After dilution with chloroform (200 ml) and chilling with ice, the solution was washed with cold water (3 times) and saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. Solvent removal after drying left a foamy solid which was crystallized from diethyl ether. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ (ppm) : 1.8 (3H, s, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 2.0 (3H, s, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 2.21 (3H, s, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 4.0–4.35 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 4.7 (1H, dd, $-\text{CH}$), 5.1 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}$), 6.2 (1H, d, $-\text{CH}$, J 8.0 Hz), 7.8 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}$), 8.0 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}$).

Phthalimido glycoside of β -sitosterol (4) : To a mixture of compound 3 (1.2 eq, 700 mg) in dichloromethane and β -sitosterol (1 eq, 500 mg), AgClO_4 (1.2 eq, 218 mg) and Ag_2CO_3 (1.5 eq, 435 mg) were added. Molecular sieves (4 Å) were added to the reaction mixture to remove moisture from it. The reaction mixture was kept on overnight stirring. The formation of product was monitored through TLC. The crude mixture was passed through celite by diluting it several times with DCM. The filtrate was concentrated over rotary evaporator. The crude mixture was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (100–200 mesh). The mobile phase used was increasing gradient of ethyl acetate in petroleum ether. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ (ppm) : 0.96–1.9 (48H, m, $-\text{CH}$, $-\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.04 (3H, s, $-\text{COCH}_3$), 2.11 (3H, s, $-\text{COCH}_3$), 2.27 (3H, s, $-\text{COCH}_3$), 3.9–4.2 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 4.86 (1H, dd, $-\text{CH}$), 4.95 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}$), 5.1 (1H, t, $=\text{CH}-$ in β -sitosterol), 5.57 (1H, d, $-\text{CH}$, J 8.47 Hz), 7.7 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}$), 7.9 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}$).

Deprotection of phthalimido group (5) : To compound 4, equal amount of butanol and hydrazine hydrate were added. The mixture was kept on refluxing for 14 h. The solvent was then evaporated and to this equal amount of Ac_2O and pyridine were added. Small amount of 4-dimethylaminopyridine crystals were also added as catalyst. The reaction mixture was then kept on stirring for few hours. The solvent was then evaporated using rotary evaporator. Pure product was obtained by subjecting the crude product to column chromatography. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ (ppm) : 0.96–1.75 (48H, m, $-\text{CH}$,

$-\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.19 (3H, s, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 2.25 (3H, s, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 2.4 (3H, s, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 2.6 (3H, s, $-\text{COCH}_3$), 3.7–4.0 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 4.7 (1H, dd, $-\text{CH}$), 4.9 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}$), 5.2 (1H, t, $=\text{CH}-$ in β -sitosterol), 6.1 (1H, d, $-\text{CH}$, J 8.47 Hz), 7.5 (1H, d, $-\text{NH}$).

Deprotection of acetyl groups of glucosamine (6) : Compound 5 was taken in methanol (HPLC) and stoichiometric amount of sodium methoxide dissolved in methanol was added and reaction mixture was kept for 3 h. Deacetylation of product was monitored through TLC. IR-20H⁺ resin was added to quench the reaction and then the reaction mixture was filtered and concentrated using rotary evaporator. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ (ppm) : 1.1–2.3 (48H, m, $-\text{CH}$, $-\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.1 (3H, m, $-\text{OH}$), 2.3 (3H, s, $-\text{COCH}_3$), 3.4–3.8 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}-\text{OH}$), 4.7 (1H, dd, $-\text{CH}$), 5.0 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}$), 5.2 (1H, t, $=\text{CH}-$ in β -sitosterol), 5.9 (1H, d, $-\text{CH}$, J 7.9 Hz), 7.9 (1H, d, $-\text{NH}$).

References

1. D. H. Miles and U. Kolpol, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1976, **65**, 284.
2. K. Fritz and L. Elmadfa, *Ann. Nutr. Metab.*, 2008, **52**, 47.
3. J. J. Argen, E. Tvrzicka, M. T. Nenone, T. Helve and O. Hanninen, *Br. J. Nutr.*, 2001, **85**, 137.
4. Z. Ovesna, A. Vachalkova and K. Horvathova, *Neoplasma*, 2004, **51**, 407.
5. P. Muti, A. B. Awad, H. Schunemann, C. S. Fink, K. Hovey, J. L. Freudenheim, Y. W. Wu, C. Bellati, V. Pala and F. Berrino, *J. Nutrition.*, 2003, **133**, 4252.
6. S. Darshan and R. Doreswamy, *Phytotherapy Research*, **18**, 343.
7. E. C. Huskisson, *J. Int. Med. Res.*, 2008, **36**, 1161.
8. P. J. Bouie and J. H. Lamprecht, *Altern. Med. Rev.*, 1999, **4**, 170.
9. S. Dahmer and M. Schiller, *Am. Fam. Physician.*, 2008, **78**, 471.
10. G. J. Boons and K. J. Hale, "Organic Synthesis with Carbohydrates", Wiley-Blackwell Publishers, 2000, pp. 51–53.
11. S. H. Khan and R. A. Neill, "Modern Methods in Carbohydrate Synthesis", Harwood Academic Publishers, 1996, pp. 120–136.